

Destructive Interference of Light - Where Does the Energy Go?

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Abstract

We already know the unconventional and inexplicable behavior of light/photons (and other quantum particles such as electrons) in the Which-Way quantum experiment and entanglement phenomena. In this paper we propose another quantum experiment using a Michelson interferometer. We start with an 'elementary' thought experiment. Suppose that a Michelson interferometer is set up so that the two light beams undergo complete constructive interference, with a single bright spot. Then the distance of one of the mirrors is slightly adjusted for a complete destructive interference: the bright spot disappears. The puzzle is: where does the light go? We suspect that, just like nature does not allow us to know which slit a photon has passed through in the double-slit experiment, nature may not allow us to know 'where the light goes' in the case of (complete) destructive interference. Although nature may not allow a direct measurement, we can understand by reasoning 'where the light goes' during complete destructive interference. This paper reveals the mystery. A simple quantum experiment based on the Michelson interferometer is proposed.

Introduction

The behavior of quantum particles such as photons and electrons has puzzled physicists for decades. Some of these are the Which-Way quantum experiment, quantum entanglement and wave function collapse.

One of the elementary phenomena that have no explanation to date, despite the claimed advance/success of theoretical physics, is related to interference of light: where does the energy go during complete destructive interference? Is the law of conservation of energy violated? This is even more puzzling when we think of a hypothetical experiment of complete destructive interference of the electron wave. (Such an experiment can be actually difficult to design and perform). Would this violate the law of conservation of matter?

This is a fairly well-known puzzle which is rarely discussed in mainstream physics today, not because physicists are not puzzled by it but because mainstream does not want to publicly admit that such an 'elementary' problem has no explanation in current physics, which would contradict all the promotions being made about modern physics.

However, there are still some genuine scientists in the mainstream[1] who are open minded enough to discuss the reality, and this has been one of the motivations to write this paper.

This puzzle occasionally came to my mind in the past until I found the mystery behind quantum phenomena[2]. Once I found the quantum mystery, the puzzle of 'where the energy goes' during complete destructive interference of light was automatically solved.

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Complete destructive interference of light in a Michelson interferometer

Consider a Michelson interferometer shown below. At first suppose that there is a complete constructive interference, with a single bright spot. Then suppose that one of the arms is adjusted by a half-wavelength (or integral multiples of it). We know that this will cause complete destructive interference: the bright spot disappears. The puzzle is: where does the energy (the energy) go?

Fig.1

In the YouTube video[1], the author proposed that the light (energy) that disappears from the initially bright spot appears somewhere else: reflected back into the source. For this, he added a beam-splitter as shown below to form a second interference pattern. What he demonstrated was that when the bright spot disappears from the first point, it appears at the second point and vice versa.

Fig.2

At first it seems this would finally solve the puzzle. But then he came up with another puzzle: since the phase difference between the two light beams is always the same along the path, how can there be complete destructive interference at one place and constructive interference at another place? He left the viewers with this puzzle in a YouTube video posted ten years ago. So the idea that the energy that disappears from the initially bright spot will appear somewhere else has not basically solved the problem: it only led to another problem which needs a solution itself.

Solving the mystery

The solution to the mystery is this:

Light is not emitted from the source in the first place during complete destructive interference. The mystery that has eluded physicists so far is that, if there is going to be complete destructive interference, light will not be emitted from the source in the first place. Light is emitted from the source only during constructive interference. Generally, photons are emitted from the source only towards points of constructive interference (with varying degrees of interference). Unconventionally, photons are not emitted at all towards points of complete destructive interference. The current (wrong) understanding is implicitly based on classical thinking that the two light waves independently travel to the detecting screen, where they interfere destructively (or constructively).

But this leads to the question: how does the source 'know' that there will be a complete destructive interference, so as to 'decide' not to emit light? Does the source have a

'foreknowledge' that destructive interference will occur? The profound implication of this puzzle is this: the direct intervention of God in the universe, hence a scientific proof of God.

A Michelson interferometer quantum experiment

One might think of testing the above hypothesis: that light is not emitted from the source during complete destructive interference. The way to test this would be to put a detector between the light source and the beam-splitter of the interferometer, as shown below. This would enable measuring the intensity of light entering the interferometer during complete destructive interference. The detector should read zero, according to the above hypothesis.

Fig.3

The detector consists of a beam-splitter (BS3) and a light detector. A beam-splitter with a splitting ratio of (95%:5%) is placed in front of the beam-splitter of the interferometer, with 5% of the light going to a light detector. It is important that the ratio of transmitted to reflected light be as high as possible. This is because the beam-splitter will also cause a second interference pattern (bright spot) and we want the intensity of this to be as small as possible. From the intensity of light detected by the detector, the intensity of light going to the interferometer can be inferred.

But this will 'work' only until it is tested. From our past experience of quantum phenomena, I suspect that the moment the detector is placed between the source and the interferometer, the interference fringe will disappear, just like in the Which-Way experiment. All we will see with

the detector in place is a bright spot. The two light beams stop interfering. But what is the basis for this claim?

This idea occurred to me after I saw the YouTube video [1] I mentioned earlier. The fact that the bright spot appears at the second point when it disappears from the first point made me suspect that some kind of strange quantum phenomena we know in the Which-Way and other quantum experiments may be at play in this experiment also.

But why does this happen? Perhaps God does not want us to make a direct measurement to know 'where the light energy is going', or to directly test that light is not emitted during complete destructive interference. He may want us to just believe it? Although we cannot make a direct measurement, we can understand what is going on by reasoning.

Now returning to the experiment [1], consider the light reflected back into the laser. Consider a laser source emitting the light beam towards a mirror which reflects the light directly towards the laser, i.e. the plane of the mirror is perpendicular to the light beam. The current universal understanding is that, conventionally, the source emits the light (energy), which is reflected back from the mirror into the laser. This is wrong. The new theory proposed in this paper is that no light is actually emitted towards the mirror in this case because there is nothing that absorbs the light energy on its path. The mirror would ideally reflect back all the incident light and will absorb zero energy. Therefore, there is no light emitted from the source in the first place.

Several arguments could be made against this hypothesis. One may argue that a standing wave will be formed which can be detected and that this is evidence that there is a forward propagating light wave (energy) and a backward propagating wave.

Nature is so elusive. Light will be emitted only when the SWR detector is placed in the path. One might think that the full intensity of light is emitted when the detector is there. No. Only a small amount of energy that can be absorbed in the detector is emitted. The amount of light actually emitted is only a tiny fraction of the nominal light intensity of the laser. However, this is inaccessible to direct experimental proof.

Therefore, the explanation that the energy that disappears from the initially bright spot goes back into the laser is wrong. One may ask: then where does the energy in the second bright spot come from? The explanation is this: that energy is available only when we detect it (as was done by using a beam splitter and a screen).

And why does the bright spot appear in one place when it disappears from the other place? The phase difference of the two light beams is supposed to be the same everywhere along the path, because the light beams are the 'same' (in the words of the author) ?

The solution to this puzzle lies in the word 'the same'. This is the prevailing fallacy in physics, which is still trapped in classical thinking despite being 'modern'. There is a hidden 'ether thinking' in this view. The mystery that has eluded physicists is that the light is not 'the same'. Every photon is aimed to be detected at a specific point in space.

The path length of the light beams is of the order of one million times the wavelength of light. Therefore, the phase difference between the two light beams at any point is determined by probability, and not by classical laws. This is to say that the fact that the two light beams are in phase at one point and out of phase at another point should not be much of a puzzle in light of the quantum nature of light we discussed so far. This is because quantum principles, and not classical principles, govern all optical and quantum phenomena.

However, I also propose an alternative outcome. With the detector put in place (Fig.3), the interference pattern will not disappear and there is no change of the detector output. This would imply an *apparent* non-conservation of energy. There will be no energy going from the source to the detecting screen during complete destructive interference, but there will be a small energy going to the detector *as if* light was going to the detecting screen. This would be inaccessible to experimental verification.

Light interference pattern

So far we have considered the case of complete constructive or destructive interference. In most cases, however, we have interference patterns, which occur when there is neither complete constructive interference nor complete destructive interference. What I have observed is that an experimental setup for complete constructive or destructive interference necessarily results in the light beam being reflected back (conventionally thinking) into the source, and this allows for a conventional argument that the light reflects back into the source during complete destructive interference, as discussed above. Although I have presented arguments against this conventional view, a more decisive disproof of this conventional view is needed. This requires an experimental setup in which the light does not reflect back into the source. Such experimental setups always create interference patterns, as shown below.

Fig.4

The argument is as follows. Suppose that initially there is some interference pattern, with alternating bright and dark fringes. For this, the difference in the path lengths of the two beams should be less than the coherence length of the source. Then the position of one of the mirrors is adjusted slightly. This will cause a change in the interference pattern. In general, the *total* light energy in the first interference pattern will be different (greater or smaller) from the *total* light energy in the second pattern. Suppose that the energy in the second pattern (E_2) is less than the energy in the first pattern (E_1) . The question is: where does the net energy ($E_1 - E_2$) go? Thus,

unlike the case of complete destructive interference, this experimental setup eliminates any conventional explanation because there is no light reflected back into the source.

A proposed experiment to test apparent non-conservation of energy

Suppose that in the above experiment a sensor is put in place of the detecting screen. The sensor could be a small photovoltaic panel with a resistor load attached to its output. As the interference fringes change due to adjustment of the mirror, the current and voltage output of the photovoltaic panel could be monitored. The sensor could also be a small water container with black outer surface to absorb the light energy. The temperature of the water is monitored as the interference fringes change. Any fluctuation of the sensor output will show an *apparent* non-conservation of energy. What actually happens is that the number of photons that are emitted from the source varies with change of interference pattern, hence no violation of energy conservation law.

The theories discussed so far applies not only to light and quantum particles, but also fundamentally to all electromagnetic waves.

Conclusion

In this paper, two related theories have been proposed:

1. Light is not emitted from the source during complete destructive interference.
2. But this is inaccessible to direct experimental test. (This one may be a reasonable speculation)

We have seen that the phenomenon of (destructive) interference of light is a direct scientific evidence of God.

Thanks to Almighty God Jesus Christ and His Mother Our Lady Saint Virgin Mary

References

1. Optics: Destructive interference - Where does the light go? by Professor Shaoul Ezekiel

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RRi4dv9KgCg&lc=UgzRc-ijzHrALNbE3VV4AaABAq>

2. Light Speed, Absolute Motion and Quantum Phenomena- Does Nature Have a Foreknowledge of Observer's Motions and Actions? Scientific Proof of God. , by Henok Tadesse

<https://www.vixra.org/abs/2007.0162>